

$\mu=0.2 M$ (KNO_3). HMMCO has also been used by us to prepare metal chelates for studying their tentative geometry²⁻⁴ and in the extraction of some metal ions⁵.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. The ligand HMMCO was prepared by the known method⁸. Metal nitrates were dissolved in double distilled water and metal contents were estimated volumetrically by titrating against standard EDTA solution using suitable indicator.

The experimental method employed consists of pH titration of the following three mixtures, in three different vessels⁹, thermostated at 25°, against standard 1.0 M NaOH solution: (A) $-1.92 \times 10^{-2} M$ HNO_3 ; (B) $-(A) + 4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand (HMMCO) and (C) $-(B) + 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal solution. KNO_3 solution was added to each mixture to maintain ionic strength at $\mu=0.2 M$ and the total volume was adjusted to 100 ml in each case with the solvent. A 50% v/v dioxane-water mixture was used as the solvent.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand stability constant of HMMCO was determined by plotting \bar{n}_A vs pH. From this plot the $\log K^H$ was determined as 12.12, which is in good agreement with the value reported earlier⁵.

During metal solution titration, precipitation was observed in Co(II) and Ni(II) systems at pH 7.5, while in the Cu(II) system no precipitate was observed. The stability constants of the metal chelates were determined using Bjerrum-Calvin pH meter titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁶. The various methods (half \bar{n} value, least squares method, interpolations at various \bar{n} values) were used to compute stability constants. The values of stability constants obtained by the three methods were nearly the same. Table 1 contains the stability constant values obtained by interpolation at various \bar{n} values for Co(II) and Ni(II) systems and by least squares method for Cu(II) system.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Complex	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_n$
Co(II)	7.41	—	7.41
Ni(II)	7.73	—	7.73
Cu(II)	10.58	8.88	19.46

It can be concluded from the results in Table 1 that the order of the stability constants ($\log K_1$) of the complexes in the present investigation is $Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II)$ which is in harmony with Irving Williams order⁷. $\log K_2$ values of Ni(II)-HMMCO and Co(II)-HMMCO systems could not be

obtained due to precipitation during titration at higher pH (>7.5). The order of stability observed in the present investigation is in good agreement with the earlier workers^{1,2}.

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Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of Trivalent Praseodymium and Neodymium Complexes with Glutamic acid : A Polarographic Study

FARID KHAN and A. V. MAHAJANI*

Department of Chemistry, University of Saugar,
Sagar-470 003

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STABILITY constants and thermodynamic parameters of rare earths complexes with glutamic acid have been determined by different authors using different methods¹⁻⁴. A survey of literature reveals that no work has so far been done on rare earths complexes with glutamic acid by the polarographic method. The stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of rare earths complexes with glutamic acid, obtained by the polarographic technique, are being reported here.

Experimental

A. R. grade chemicals were used to prepare all the solutions. Stock solutions of praseodymium(III) and neodymium(III) were prepared by dissolving the calculated quantity of metal oxides in minimum quantity of hydrochloric acid (AnalaR). The metal solution was standardised with EDTA⁵. The overall concentrations of potassium chloride, gelatin and

rare earth metal ions in the test electrolytic solution were kept constant at 1.0 M, 0.01% and 2 mM, respectively. The ligand concentration was varied from 1.0 mM to 10 mM. The ionic strength was fixed at 1.0 M, adjusting with potassium chloride. Hydrochloric acid was used to adjust the pH of the solution at 2.4 ± 0.02 .

An automatic pen recording (C. I. C., Baroda, India) polarograph was used to record the polarograms. The capillary used had an m value of 2.15 mg/sec and drop time of 3.0 sec, when measured in an air free 1.0 M potassium chloride at 31.0 cm effective height of the mercury column. Pure nitrogen gas was used for deoxygenating the solution before recording the polarograms. All measurements were carried out at 25 and 35° in thermostat.

Results and Discussion

Praseodymium(III) and neodymium(III) give well defined three electron reversible reduction waves at pH 2.4⁶⁻⁷ in 1.0 M potassium chloride, with 0.01% gelatin being used as a maximum suppressor. The nature of the waves for metal ions and their complexes was found to be diffusion controlled as revealed from linear plots of i_d vs \sqrt{t} . The reduction of praseodymium(III) and neodymium(III) at pH 2.4 ± 0.02 were at -1.81 V and -1.79 V vs SCE. The log plot slope values for the metal ions and their complexes was 20 ± 1 mV indicating the reversibility of the electrode process.

The half wave potential shifted to more negative values on gradual increase of ligand concentration. A Lingane⁸ treatment of the data revealed the formation of 1 : 1 complexes for praseodymium(III) and neodymium(III) with glutamic acid. The values of stability constant and thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES AT $\mu=1.0$ M POTASSIUM CHLORIDE

		25°	35°
Metal ligand stability constant (log K)	Praseodymium(III)	4.00	3.81
	Neodymium(III)	5.30	5.11
Change in enthalpy (ΔH) in k cal/mole	Praseodymium(III)	-8.04*	
	Neodymium(III)	-3.21*	
Change in free energy (ΔG) in k cal/mole	Praseodymium(III)	-5.52	-5.43
	Neodymium(III)	-7.31	-7.29
Change in entropy (ΔS) in cal/degree/mole	Praseodymium(III)	-8.41	-8.42
	Neodymium(III)	-3.00	-2.29

* For the difference of 10°.

The order of stability constants of the metal ions is praseodymium(III) < neodymium(III). The increase of stability constants from praseodymium(III) to neodymium(III) is mainly due to lanthanide contraction.

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Thermodynamics and Stability Constants of Ce(III) Complexes with Crotonic, Cinnamic, Itaconic and Citraconic Acids :

A Polarographic Study

FARID KHAN, V. K. CHITALE and A. V. MAHAJANI

Department of Chemistry, University of Sangar,
Sagar-470 008

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POLAROGRAPHY has been used for the complexation study of Pr(III) and Nd(III) with some unsaturated acids¹⁻⁴. In continuation, we now report thermodynamic parameters and stability constants of the complexes of Ce(III) with crotonic, cinnamic, itaconic and citraconic acids on a dropping mercury electrode.

Experimental

A. R. grade chemicals were used to prepare the solutions. The solutions of ligands were prepared in double distilled water. The solution of the metal ion was prepared by dissolving the calculated quantity of $CeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Fluka A. G., Switzerland) in double distilled water and was standardized with EDTA⁵. The concentrations of Ce(III), potassium chloride and gelatin in the test electrolytic solution were fixed at 2.0 mM, 1.0 M and 0.01%, respectively. The concentration of the ligand was varied from 1.0 mM to 10.0 mM in each case. Ionic strength was fixed at $\mu=1.0$ adjusted with potassium chloride. Hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide were used to adjust the pH of the test solution at 2.75 ± 0.02 .

Polarograms were recorded on a automatic pen recording (C. I. C., Baroda, India) polarograph. The capillary used had an m value = 2.16 mg/sec and drop time 3.10 sec at 43.0 cm effective height of the